

EVALUATION OF THE STATE OF MICROBIOCENOSIS OF THE ORAL CAVITY IN
PATIENTS WITH PARODONTAL DISEASES¹Kurbanova S.Y., ²Nigmatova I.M., ³Alisherova Z.T.^{1,2,3}Tashkent State Dental Institute<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8357965>

Аннотация. В ходе микробиологического исследования нами был изучен состав микрофлоры зубо-десневой борозды у 61 пациента. Установлено, что количественный и видовой состав специфической микрофлоры не всегда коррелирует с данными клинических проявлений заболевания.

Оценить микрофлору можно традиционным методом бактериологического исследования, но наиболее эффективным методом полной оценки уровня и ассоциации пародонтопатогенных микроорганизмов считается молекулярно-генетический метод.

На основании анализа данных, полученных с использованием метода ПЦР в зависимости от тяжести заболевания, установлено, что у больных частота выявления носительства пародонтопатогенных видов имеет прогностический характер в воспалительном процессе в тканях пародонта на фоне снижения общей резистентности макроорганизма.

Ключевые слова: пародонтит, иммунитет, микроорганизмы, этиология, патогенез

Annotatsiya. Mikrobiologik tadqiqot davomida biz 61 bemorda tish sulkusi mikroflorasining tarkibini o'rgandik. Muayyan mikrofloraning miqdoriy va o'ziga xos tarkibi har doim ham kasallikning klinik ko'rinishlari ma'lumotlari bilan bog'liq emasligi aniqlandi.

Mikroflorani an'anaviy bakteriologik tadqiqot usuli bilan baholash mumkin, ammo periodontopatogen mikroorganizmlar darajasi va assotsiatsiyasini to'liq baholashning eng samarali usuli molekulyar genetik usuldir.

PZR usuli yordamida olingan ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilish asosida, kasallikning og'irligiga qarab, bemorlarda periodontal patogen turlarni aniqlash chastotasi makroorganizmning umumiy qarshiligining pasayishi fonida periodontal to'qimalarda yallig'lanish jarayonida prognostik xarakterga ega ekanligi aniqlandi.

Kalit so'zlar: periodontit, иммунитет, микроорганизмы, yetiologiya, patogenez

Abstract. In the course of a microbiological study, we studied the composition of the microflora of the dentogingival sulcus in 61 patients. It has been established that the quantitative and species composition of the specific microflora does not always correlate with the data of the clinical manifestations of the disease.

The microflora can be assessed by the traditional method of bacteriological research, but the molecular genetic method is considered the most effective method for a complete assessment of the level and association of periodontopathogenic microorganisms.

Based on the analysis of data obtained using the PCR method, depending on the severity of the disease, it was found that in patients the frequency of detection of carriage of periodontopathogenic species is prognostic in the inflammatory process in periodontal tissues against the background of a decrease in the overall resistance of the macroorganism.

Keywords: periodontitis, immunity, microorganisms, etiology, pathogenesis

The high prevalence of inflammatory periodontal diseases is due to insufficient diagnosis, the course of inflammatory periodontal diseases is particularly resistant to treatment, which determines the significance and relevance of this problem in modern dentistry [6].

One of the important problems of modern dentistry is the early diagnosis of periodontal tissue diseases, since their prevalence remains quite high and already in childhood is 50% [4,6]. According to modern data, periodontal diseases often occur against the background of endocrine and immunological changes and are accompanied by a violation of metabolic processes in periodontal tissues [1,5,6].

Today, it is generally accepted that periodontal tissue diseases are multifactorial, the development of which is associated with hereditary predisposition, microbial effects, hormonal, neurogenic disorders, and are realized by a polygenic system, which includes features of the immune response and type of metabolism.

Periodontal pockets serve as a habitat for many microorganisms. Some of them are periodontopathogenic and can cause gingivitis and periodontitis. Quantitative assessment of the ratio of different periodontopathogenic microbes in the studied biocenosis is an important diagnostic tool. However, the representation profile of the most pathogenic representatives of periodontal pocket microbiocenosis in normal conditions and in periodontitis is still poorly understood [1,2,3,4,6].

Purpose of the study. Conduct a comparative assessment of the effectiveness of classical and molecular genetic methods for diagnosing inflammatory periodontal diseases.

In the course of a microbiological study, we studied the composition of the microflora of the periodontal sulcus in 61 patients.

Sampling was carried out from the periodontal sulcus using sterile discs after 2 minutes of contact exposure, then they were placed in test tubes with 1 ml of sugar broth, 0.1 ml of which was sown on nutrient media. Within 24 hours after incubation in a thermostat ($t=37^{\circ}\text{C}$), the number of grown colonies on a dish was counted and recalculated per 1 cm^2 of area.

When studying microbiocenosis, standard nutrient media were used: - blood agar - to calculate the total microbial contamination; - yolk-salt agar - for staphylococci; - sugar broth - for streptococci; - vegetable-milk environment - for lactobacilli; - Saburo's medium - for yeast-like fungi of the genus *Candida*. The inoculations on traditional nutrient media were incubated in a thermostat for 2 days, and on Sabouraud medium for about 3 days.

To study the anaerobic microflora, the flasks with the test samples were placed in a microanaerostat of the Gas-Pak system. After preparation, a series of serial dilutions, of which 0.1 ml of the test material was inoculated on appropriate nutrient media and grown in a thermostat at a temperature of 37°C .

Phenotypic identification of microorganisms was carried out using digital coding of the trait based on the study of glucose fermentation, cytochrome oxidase, motility, growth on Simmons citrate and sodium malonate, glucose breakdown with the formation of gas, indole, hydrogen sulfide, phenylalanine deaminase, lysine and ornithine decarboxylase, urea hydrolysis, arginine dehydrolyase, lactose fermentation, mannitol, sucrose, sorbitol, inositol, rhamnose, xylose, maltose, arabinose.

Real-time polymerase chain reaction (PCR) was used in parallel with classical bacteriological methods to detect obligate anaerobic microorganisms of the oral cavity. Biomaterial samples were taken using sterile paper strips 0.5–10 mm in size, and the resulting

material was placed in test tubes with a transport medium for bioassays. Using a set of reagents, 5 periodontopathogenic microorganisms were identified (*Actinobacillus actinomycetemcomitans*, *Porphyromonas gingivalis*, *Prevotella intermedia*, *Tannerella forsythensis* (*Bacteroides forsythus*), *Treponema denticola*) и *Candida albicans*).

Analysis of data from microbiological studies of plaque samples in patients, depending on the quantitative and qualitative composition of the oral microflora, made it possible to identify the presence of representatives belonging to the normal coccal flora in 90% of cases, the proportion of which was 78.3% of strains. Regardless of the clinical state of periodontal tissues in patients with plaque samples in 57.4% of cases, diplococci were detected, in 13.1% of cases - colonies of cocci, associations of cocci with actinomycetes - in 37.2% of cases.

Among the representatives of microorganisms belonging to the autochthonous flora, representatives of non-resident microflora were detected in small numbers - *Staphylococcus aureus* and pyogenic streptococcus, enterococci.

So, as a result of microbiological studies, it was found that in 61 periodontal pockets studied by the content of dentogingival fluid, the following associations of aerobic microflora were identified: in 17 - *Staphylococcus aureus*, in 21 - *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, in 9 - *Candida albicans*, in 4 - *Staphylococcus anhaemolyticus*, and in 10 - *Streptococcus spp.*

Thus, in the examined patients with periodontal tissue diseases, 5 varieties of aerobic microflora associations were found, which indicates a significant colonization of the mucous membrane with both saprophytic and conditionally pathogenic flora, compared with healthy ones.

When analyzing the data obtained by PCR, in the studied samples of plaque and samples from the periodontal sulcus, monoinfection with *P. gingivalis* was observed only in 21 patients, which accounted for 34.4% of cases, in 18 patients (29.5% of cases) associations of two species of periodontopathogenic microorganism species (*Treponema denticola* + *B. forsythus*), in 22 patients the combined carriage of three representatives of periodontal pathogenic species (*P. gingivalis* + *Treponema denticola* + *B. forsythus*) was determined, which accounted for 36.0% of cases.

Analysis of the data obtained using microbiological methods depending on the severity made it possible to distribute the clinical groups into subgroups:

Group I - (15 patients with mild severity). In clinical subgroups of individuals diagnosed mild periodontal disease in the analysis, 1-2-3 component associations were identified in 46.6%; 33.3%; 20%.

In 46.6% of patients (7) *P. gingivalis* monoinfection was observed; in 33.3% (5) associations of two species were determined: *Treponema denticola* + *B. forsythus*, in 3 in 20% of cases - associations of three species: *P. gingivalis* + *Treponema denticola* + *B. forsythus*.

II group - 22 (36%). When analyzing the structure of markers isolated from plaque samples in patients with a moderate course of the disease, it was found that *P. gingivalis* markers were detected most often (26.3%), *B. forsythus* and *T. denticola* in 13.8% of cases. Microorganisms in 57.1% of cases were mainly represented by associations of three species, in 14.3% - by associations of two, and in 28.6% - of four species.

Group III - 24 (39.3%). In clinical subgroups with severe disease from the oral mucosa, 1-2 component associations were identified in 21.3%, 2-3 and 3-4 component associations in 46.1% of cases, 4-5 component associations in 32.6% of cases. . The complication of microbial

associations found in the area of the gingival margin contributed to the progression and aggravation of chronic periodontal diseases.

Conclusion. Against the background of a chronic inflammatory process, favorable conditions are created for the development of pathogenic microflora, which in turn leads to the support of inflammatory processes in periodontal tissues. The results of microbiological studies give reason to believe that in the treatment of periodontal tissue diseases in patients with different severity of the disease, not only the severity of the disease, but also the species composition of the microflora should be taken into account. This approach is expedient and rational in the choice of antibacterial drugs in complex treatment, having previously determined the sensitivity of the microflora of the oral cavity to them. The method of molecular genetic diagnostics established the relationship between the detection of *Porphyromonas gingivalis*, *Treponema denticola*, *Streptococcus mutans*, *Streptococcus oralis*, *Streptococcus salivarius*, *Streptococcus sanguis*, *Streptococcus sobrinus* and their associations with a high frequency in moderate and severe periodontitis

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